

Formulating Competency Questions as SPARQL Queries

Id	Competency Question	SPARQL Query	Results
CQ1	Which community smells are associated with the socio-technical factors that give rise to social debt?	<pre>PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?Domain ?DomainLabel ?CommunitySmell WHERE { ?cause rdf:type ?Domain . ?Domain rdfs:subClassOf+ :Cause . ?cause :hasRelatedCommunitySmell ?CommunitySmell . OPTIONAL { ?Domain rdfs:label ?DomainLabel } } ORDER BY ?Domain ?CommunitySmell</pre>	The query returns a set of domain–community-smell pairs, listing, for each social-debt cause domain (AdministrativeCause, CommunicationCause, CoordinationCause, CollaborationCause, CongruenceCause), the community smells linked to cause instances via the :hasRelatedCommunitySmell property.
CQ2	What causes, linked to a specific socio-technical factor, influence the emergence and management of social debt?	<pre>PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?Domain ?CauseID ?CauseName WHERE { ?cause rdf:type ?Domain . ?Domain rdfs:subClassOf* :Cause . OPTIONAL { ?cause :hasCauseID ?CauseID } # ID user-defined OPTIONAL { ?cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName }# User-defined name } ORDER BY ?Domain ?CauseID</pre>	Lists social debt causes by domain (Communication, Collaboration, Coordination, Congruence, and Administration), including their ID and name.
CQ3	Which socio-technical factors are affected by social debt?	<pre>PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?Domain ?DomainName WHERE { ?cause rdf:type ?Domain . ?Domain rdfs:subClassOf* :Cause . OPTIONAL { ?Domain rdfs:label ?DomainName } } ORDER BY ?DomainName</pre>	The query retrieves each cause domain and its corresponding label, listing the distinct categories in which the causes of social debt are grouped.

CQ4	What effects does a cause of social debt produce within the context of a particular sociotechnical factor?	<pre> PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?Domain ?CauseName ?EffectName WHERE { ?cause rdf:type :CommunicationCause . # ← Change here for another domain ?cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName . ?cause :generatesEffect ?effect . ?effect :hasEffectName ?EffectName . BIND(:CommunicationCause AS ?Domain)} ORDER BY ?CauseName ?EffectName </pre>	The query identifies the effects generated by social debt causes within a specific domain (e.g., Communication), linking each cause to its effect using :hasCauseName and :hasEffectName.
CQ5	Which corrective strategies are associated with specific effects of social debt, according to the corresponding socio-technical factor of impact?	<pre> PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX owl: <http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?EffectType ?StrategyType ?StrategyName WHERE { ?Effect :hasEffectName "Frequent Changes in Leadership" . ?Effect rdf:type ?EffectType . FILTER(?EffectType != owl:NamedIndividual){ ?Effect :hasAdministrativeStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("AdministrativeStrategy" AS ?StrategyType)} UNION { ?Effect :hasGroupStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("GroupStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Effect :hasIndividualStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("IndividualStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Effect :hasTechnicalStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("TechnicalStrategy" AS ?StrategyType)} OPTIONAL { ?Strategy :hasStrategyName ?StrategyName . } ORDER BY ?EffectType ?StrategyType ?StrategyName </pre>	The query identified the corrective strategies associated with the effect “Frequent Changes in Leadership” in the Social Debt Ontology. The results showed that this effect is classified as GroupEffect and linked to GroupStrategy, highlighting that the proposed solutions are aimed at group-level interventions consistent with its collective nature.

CQ6	Which preventive strategies can be applied to a specific cause of social debt, according to its socio-technical factor of impact?	<pre> PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?CauseName ?StrategyType ?StrategyName WHERE { ?Cause :hasCauseName "Lack of Task Discussion" . ?Cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName .{ ?Cause :hasCommunicationStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CommunicationStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCoordinationStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CoordinationStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCollaborationStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CollaborationStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasAdministrativePStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("AdministrativePStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCongruenceStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CongruenceStrategy" AS ?StrategyType)} OPTIONAL { ?Strategy :hasStrategyName ?StrategyName . } }ORDER BY ?StrategyType ?StrategyName </pre>	The query identified the preventive strategies associated with the cause “Lack of Task Discussion”. The results showed that this cause is classified as Cause and is linked exclusively to CollaborationStrategy, indicating that the proposed solutions focus on strengthening collaboration practices consistent with its collective and interactional nature.
CQ7	Which community smells are associated with the socio-technical factors and causes that	<pre> PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> </pre>	The objective was to identify the socio-technical factors and causes that generate social debt in the development team GRP001_Research_Team_A. The
	generate social debt in a specific development team?	<pre> SELECT DISTINCT ?Domain ?CauseName ?CommunitySmell WHERE { # Causa asociada a grupo específico ?Cause :isAssociatedWithGroup :GRP001_Research_Team_A . ?Cause rdf:type ?Domain . ?Domain rdfs:subClassOf* :Cause . OPTIONAL { ?Cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName . } OPTIONAL { ?Cause :hasRelatedCommunitySmell ?CommunitySmell . } BIND(:YourGroupID AS ?GroupName)} ORDER BY ?Domain ?CauseName ?CommunitySmell </pre>	results showed three factors—AdministrativeCause, CongruenceCause, and CoordinationCause—associated respectively with the causes “No Knowledge Transfer Policy,” “Solo Development Preference,” and “Unilateral Task Assignment.” These causes are linked to the community smells “Truck Factor” and “Prima Donnas”.

CQ8	What negative effects does the presence of a specific community smell have on team members, the organization, or software quality?	<pre> PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?CauseName ?EffectType ?EffectName WHERE { ?Cause :hasRelatedCommunitySmell ?SmellName . FILTER(?SmellName = "Truck Factor") # Literal exacto del olor ?Cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName . ?Cause :generatesEffect ?Effect . ?Effect rdf:type ?EffectType . ?Effect :hasEffectName ?EffectName . FILTER(?EffectType IN (:AdministrativeEffect, :GroupEffect, :IndividualEffect, :ProjectManagementEffect, :TechnicalEffect))} ORDER BY ?EffectType ?EffectName </pre>	To examine the negative effects of the community smell “Truck Factor”, the results showed impacts across organizational, group, individual, project management, and technical dimensions. These include limited support, difficulties in knowledge sharing, reduced motivation, delays, inefficient resource use, and technical issues such as duplication and lack of synchronization.
CQ9	What strategies can be applied to prevent or mitigate a specific community smell that contributes to the accumulation of social debt?	<pre> PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?CauseName ?StrategyType ?StrategyName WHERE { ?Cause :hasRelatedCommunitySmell "Truck Factor" ; :hasCauseName ?CauseName . # Vincula ?Strategy + etiqueta de tipo por cada propiedad posible { ?Cause :hasAdministrativePreventiveStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("AdministrativePreventiveStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCollaborationStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CollaborationStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCommunicationStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CommunicationStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCoordinationStrategy ?Strategy . </pre>	The query aimed to identify preventive strategies to mitigate the causes of social debt. The results showed that, to address the community smell “Truck Factor”, causes such as lack of documentation, knowledge monopoly, and insufficient peer support can be mitigated through administrative, collaboration, and congruence strategies.

		<pre> BIND("CoordinationStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } UNION { ?Cause :hasCongruenceStrategy ?Strategy . BIND("CongruenceStrategy" AS ?StrategyType) } } # Nombre de la estrategia (preferir hasStrategyName; si no, rdfs:label) OPTIONAL { ?Strategy :hasStrategyName ?n1 . } OPTIONAL { ?Strategy rdfs:label ?n2 . } BIND(COALESCE(?n1, ?n2) AS ?StrategyName) } ORDER BY ?StrategyType ?StrategyName </pre>	
CQ10	Which indicators allow the detection of a specific cause of social debt?	<pre> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?CauseName ?IndicatorName WHERE { ?Cause :hasCauseName "Lack of Task Discussion" . # ?Cause :isIndicatedByCause ?Indicator . ?Indicator :hasIndicatorName ?IndicatorName . OPTIONAL { ?Cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName . } }ORDER BY ?IndicatorName </pre>	The objective was to analyze which indicators can detect a specific cause of social debt. The results showed that the cause "Lack of Task Discussion" can be identified through the indicator "Feedback Latency Score".
CQ11	Which metrics are used to quantify the impact of a cause on the team or the organization?	<pre> PREFIX : <http://www.example.org/ontosocialdebt#> SELECT DISTINCT ?CauseName ?MetricName WHERE { ?Cause :hasCauseName "Lack of Task Discussion" . # Replace with the exact name of the cause you want to query ?Cause :isMeasuredByMetric ?Metric . ?Metric :hasMetricName ?MetricName . OPTIONAL { ?Cause :hasCauseName ?CauseName . } } ORDER BY ?MetricName </pre>	The objective was to identify metrics to quantify the impact of a specific cause of social debt. The results showed that the cause "Lack of Task Discussion" can be measured through the metric "Task Assignment Clarity Score", which assesses how clearly tasks are defined and distributed within the team, providing a quantitative view of its consequences.